

ECHOBIO-METRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EYE IN CHILDREN WITH HYPERMETROPIA

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Abstract. *Hypermetropia, or farsightedness, is a common refractive anomaly in children characterized by a shortened axial length of the eye and impaired light focus on the retina. Echobiometry, an ultrasound method for measuring eye parameters, provides important information about structural changes associated with hypermetropia. This article is dedicated to studying the echobiometric parameters of the eye in children with hypermetropia.*

Keywords: *Hypermetropia, echobiometry, axial length, children, refractive anomalies, ultrasound diagnostics, visual functions.*

ЭХОБИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ГЛАЗА У ДЕТЕЙ С ДАЛЬНОЗОРКОСТЬЮ

Аннотация. *Гиперметропия, или дальнозоркость, является распространенной рефракционной аномалией у детей, характеризующейся укороченной передне-задней осью глаза и нарушением фокусировки света на сетчатке. Эхобиометрия, метод ультразвукового измерения параметров глазного яблока, предоставляет важную информацию о структурных изменениях, связанных с гиперметропией. Настоящая статья посвящена изучению эхобиометрических параметров глазного яблока у детей с гиперметропией.*

Ключевые слова: *Гиперметропия, эхобиометрия, длина передне-задней оси, дети, рефракционные аномалии, ультразвуковая диагностика, зрительные функции.*

Introduction

Hypermetropia, or farsightedness, is one of the most common refractive anomalies in children.

It is characterized by light rays focusing behind the retina, leading to blurred vision. In children, this condition can be compensated by accommodation, but high degrees of hypermetropia or inadequate correction can lead to complications such as amblyopia or strabismus.

Echobiometry is an ultrasound method that allows precise measurement of the internal structures of the eye. This method is particularly useful for assessing the axial length of the eye,

anterior chamber depth, and lens thickness, which are crucial for the diagnosis and treatment of hypermetropia.

Hypermetropia in children often goes unnoticed, as young eyes can accommodate to compensate for refractive errors. However, delayed correction can lead to the development of amblyopia and other visual impairments. Echobiometry plays a key role in diagnosing and managing hypermetropia by providing accurate measurements, such as axial length, anterior chamber depth, and lens thickness.

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to analyze the echobiometric parameters of the eye in children with hypermetropia to identify characteristic changes and develop recommendations for diagnosis and treatment.

Methods

The study involved 100 children with hypermetropia, aged 5 to 12 years, and a control group of 50 children with normal refraction (emmetropia). Ultrasound measurements were conducted using a 10 MHz frequency device, ensuring high accuracy and resolution.

Measurement Procedure:

1. Axial Length (AL): Measured from the cornea to the retina. This is the primary parameter determining the refractive power of the eye.
2. Anterior Chamber Depth: Measured from the posterior surface of the cornea to the anterior surface of the lens.
3. Lens Thickness: Measured as the distance between the anterior and posterior surfaces of the lens.

Results

Data analysis showed that children with hypermetropia had a significantly shorter average axial length compared to the control group. This confirms that a shortened axial length is a major factor contributing to the development of hypermetropia.

Specific Results: The average axial length in children with hypermetropia was 21.5 mm, whereas in the control group it was 23.0 mm. Anterior chamber depth and lens thickness also showed differences, but they were less significant, indicating possible compensatory mechanisms.

The study results demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in axial length in children with hypermetropia compared to the control group. Anterior chamber depth and lens thickness also showed differences, although they were less pronounced. These changes correlate with the degree of hypermetropia and can serve as additional diagnostic criteria.

Discussion

The results emphasize the importance of using echobiometry for diagnosing hypermetropia in children. A shortened axial length is the primary echobiometric indicator to consider when assessing the degree of hypermetropia. These data can be useful for developing individualized treatment and correction plans.

Echobiometry can also aid in monitoring the progression of hypermetropia and the effectiveness of therapy. Early detection of structural changes in the eye allows timely correction of refractive errors and prevention of complications.

The findings confirm that echobiometry is an important tool in diagnosing hypermetropia in children. A shortened axial length is the primary echobiometric indicator associated with this refractive anomaly. Understanding these changes allows for more accurate determination of hypermetropia severity and the development of individualized treatment plans.

Conclusion

Echobiometry provides valuable data on structural changes in the eye associated with hypermetropia in children. These measurements can significantly improve diagnosis and treatment, facilitating more precise correction selection and complication prevention. The integration of echobiometry into clinical practice will enhance the quality of ophthalmic care for children with hypermetropia. Early detection and correction of hypermetropia using echobiometry can prevent complications and improve visual functions in children.

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